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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 3.1 – CONTEXT OF USE AND WORK ENVIRONMENT THREATS ANALYSIS (FIRST VERSION)

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Executive summary

In this document, we describe the methods and results of the context of use analysis and the work environment threats analysis run in THEIA^{XR} as a foundation for the transdisciplinary co-design approach. This version of the deliverable, which had originally contained only the results of UC1 and UC3 due to unforeseen delays in operator availability, has been updated to include UC2 results as well, based on the final version of this deliverable (D3.6), which was handed in in M19.

The context of use analysis was conducted using the contextual inquiry method, which combines interview and observation of users/operators in their work environment. We accompanied real operators working in their respective vehicles to get in-depth insights. We observed and interviewed six snow groomer operators in UC1, two reach stacker operators in UC2 (later followed by one more operator and a harbour terminal manager in an online workshop) and six excavator operators in UC3. The observations and interviews were used to create problem scenarios, narrative descriptions of the status quo of vehicle operation in these use cases.

The work environment hazard analysis was conducted using a variation of the Critical Incident Technique method, which focuses on investigating the correct behaviour to manage specific situations. In our case, we interviewed the vehicle operators to find out which common dangerous situations at their respective workplace they know and then analysed them further in regard to how these situations occur, if and how they can be prevented and how they can be managed. The results will be considered during the ideation of new technologies and interaction concepts to make the workplace at the controls of off-highway machines safer for operators and, if possible, also bystanders.

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1 Introduction

An essential precondition for designing suitable and easy-to-use technologies for the workplace is an in-depth knowledge of the environment, the processes, and tasks where the technology is going to be used and the people who are going to use it. These aspects of usage are collectively referred to as “context of use” in the research field of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and defined in the ISO 9241-11:2018[1]. According to this ISO standard, good usability requires specific users to be able to attain their goals with a product, service, or system effectively and efficiently in a specific context of use. Effectiveness describes the degree to which goals can be attained (precision and completeness), whereas efficiency describes the amount of effort and resources needed to attain the goals (commensurability). There is no such thing as a universally usable product, service, or system since effectiveness and efficiency always must be assessed for a certain context of use. Thus, using the example of THEIA^{XR} use case 3, systems that are present in some excavators that are currently effectively and efficiently being used, e.g., by very experienced operators on large construction sites for creating foundation pits may be entirely overwhelming or insufficient for newly trained operators working on much smaller construction sites for digging up a narrow road.

With the discipline of HCI dating back to the 1980s, having gained in importance and evolved ever since, there is a plethora of methods available for investigating the context of use. The main method we have been using for investigating the THEIA^{XR} use cases is the contextual inquiry, first described by [2], a combination of observation and interview directly at the relevant users’ workplace. This method allows for gathering both explicit knowledge (conscious actions and thoughts, motivations, attitudes, etc.) and implicit knowledge (habits, unconscious actions and processes deviating from protocol, etc.). According to [3], who compared 18 user research methods, the contextual inquiry is one of only two methods suitable for investigating all factors influencing human behaviour. In THEIA^{XR}, we conducted six contextual inquiries with snow groomer operators in Sterzing, Italy (UC1), two contextual inquiries with reach stacker operators in Ljungby, Sweden (UC2) and six contextual inquiries with excavator operators in Dresden and Glauchau, Germany (UC3).

In addition to the context of use we also investigated threats to life, vehicle, and equipment in the work environment of the use cases. Safety is a major concern in all three use cases and fatal accidents are not uncommon in any of them. While safety is not one of the main subjects of this research project, we want our technological developments to contribute to higher safety by mitigating some of these threats. To learn about threats in the respective work environments, we combined the contextual inquiries with a variation of the Critical Incident Technique (CIT), a method first described by [4]. The CIT was originally designed to investigate how humans perceive, respond to and manage certain significant events or occurrences in a process or activity [4], [5]. In our case, we used this method to gather vehicle operators’ personal accounts and knowledge of various threats in their work environment, descriptions of these threats and procedures to avoid or manage them.

The results of the context of use and work environment threat analysis will be used by the consortium to develop XR technologies and interaction concepts that aim for high usability (see deliverable D2.2, KPI 1.2) while mitigating at least three of the described safety risks (see deliverable D2.2, KPI 1.1).

2 Context of use analysis

Understanding the context of use is an essential prerequisite for designing systems with good usability (ISO 9241-11:2018). Thus, the first step of WP3 involved an analysis of the work environment, tasks, procedures and habits of the operators in the respective use cases. In the following, we describe the method used and the results of the analyses of UC1 (snow grooming), UC2 (logistics) and UC3 (construction).

2.1 Method

We used the contextual inquiry method [2] to gain a deep understanding of the context of use. This method combines observation and interview of users (operators) in their natural working environment (vehicle cabin). For an introduction to this method, also called primer, we informed the participants about the project itself, the study's goals, and data processing. Consent to the recording and data processing was either obtained in this step or ahead of the studies. We also made it clear to the operators that the study does not intend to assess their performance but to allow us to understand their working procedures, decisions, and habits.

After the primer, there was a transition, which involved equipping the operators with recording devices (see table 1) and explaining the method. The operators were instructed to continuously comment on what they aim to do while completing their tasks, what they pay attention to, their thoughts and decisions, as if they were training the researchers to operate the vehicles themselves.

Table 1: Technical setup for the contextual inquiries

Use case	Recording equipment	Comment
UC1 – Snow grooming	Head-mounted camera	Eye-tracking glasses could not be used due to technical issues. Researchers were sitting in the cabin next to operators.
UC2 – Logistics	Eye-tracking glasses, head-mounted camera	Videos from the perspective of the operators were recorded using the eye-tracking glasses and then retrospectively discussed.
UC3 – Construction	Eye-tracking glasses + in-ear headphones for remote communication via online conference; eye-tracking monitoring laptop	Excavators are single-seaters; thus, researchers used a livestream from the eye-tracking glasses to monitor the operators' point of view during vehicle operation from a nearby container. Audio was recorded both by the eye-tracking glasses (operator audio only) and a simultaneous conference call.

During the context interview itself, we followed the “watch and learn” approach, observing and listening to the operators during vehicle operation and asking questions when more information was needed to interpret the operators' actions and decisions correctly. There was no specific guideline for the tasks performed and questions asked. However, the focus of the contextual inquiries was on the previously identified use case specifications (see deliverable D2.1).

Based on the contextual inquiries, we created so-called problem scenarios according to the scenario-based design approach [6]. These problem scenarios are narrative descriptions, visualizing the status quo of vehicle operation in each use case and will serve as a foundation for the ideation of new technologies and interaction concepts for the off-highway vehicle cabins. They remain subject to change over the coming co-design activities and workshops with vehicle operators and will be continuously expanded and improved. In the next stages, the storylines of the problem scenarios will be rewritten as activity scenarios, visualizing possible future solutions for the previously described status quo, and subsequently as information scenarios and interaction scenarios, expanding the solutions in more detail.

The contextual inquiries and hazard analyses (see **chapter 3**) were conducted with a total of 16 participants, 6 in UC1, 2 in UC2 and 6 in UC3, see Table 2. All of these participants have been male, as no female vehicle operators are currently active at the respective organisations and companies that have been supporting the project so far. We will try to expand the operator community involved in the project to become more diverse in the future by contacting additional institutions or seeking out individual operators on social media.

Table 2: Participant overview

Use case	Participant	Nationality	Occupation / vehicle operation experience
UC1	S1	Italian	Operator & trainer, 20+ years of experience
	S2	Italian	Operator & trainer, 20+ years of experience
	S3	Italian	Operator in training, 1–2 years of experience
	S4	Italian	Operator & trainer, 5–10 years of experience
	S5	Italian	Operator & tester, 5–10 years of experience
	S6	Italian	Operator & tester, 20+ years of experience
UC2	L1	Swedish	Tester & demo driver, 10+ years of experience
	L2	Swedish	Tester & demo driver, 10+ years of experience
	L3*	Finnish	Operator, 10+ years of experience
	L4*	Finnish	Terminal & technical manager, no vehicle experience
UC3	C1	German	Researcher, occasional vehicle use
	C2	German	Researcher, occasional vehicle use
	C3	German	Operator & trainer, 10+ years of experience
	C4	German	Operator & trainer, 10+ years of experience
	C5	German	Training manager, trainer, 20+ years of experience
	C6	German	Simulator trainer, occasional vehicle use

*Participants were not part of the contextual inquiries, but consulted later for additional validation

2.2 Use case 1: Snow grooming

For UC1, we created a problem scenario around fictional snow groomer operator Marco on a typical workday. This problem scenario is based on our observations of five experienced snow groomer operators and one newly trained operator.

Table 3: UC1 problem scenario

Scenario chapter	Story
Preparations	Marco meets with the other operators and quickly discusses who will groom which slopes.
Start of snow grooming	Marco does a quick safety inspection of the machine, starts the engine and checks if all the systems are working. He drives up to the slope, moves blade and tiller in position and starts grooming the first lane uphill (for example, see Figure 1). In the lower part of the slope, the snow is soft and light, therefore, he drives slowly and sets the tiller to low pressure.
Blade accident	Marco accidentally set the blade too low while driving down the slope and ripped a hole into the ground where snow is now mixed with the soil. He needs to reverse and fill the hole with snow from a different part of the slope. Finding a good spot to collect surplus snow and fixing the hole takes him quite some time.
Bad vision	Night falls and heavy snowfall sets in. Marco can only see around 10–20m ahead and is forced to navigate by the trees and markings on the side of the slope. He can barely see which lanes have already been prepared and needs to look very closely in front of the machine. While navigating through snowfall, he barely hits an unknown object in front of him which has already been covered in snow. Marco steps out of the vehicle to inspect the object, which after removing some snow turns out to be a small transport trailer left behind by a snowmobile.
Winch operation	The snowfall has subsided and Marco approaches a steep part of the slope where he needs to use the winch. He slowly drives towards the upper edge of the slope, gets out of the vehicle, and attaches the winch cable to the anchor point. Then he re-enters the vehicle and slowly descends the slope. As he descends the slope, he notices two skiers in the left side mirror somewhere behind him. Annoyed and concerned that they might get too close to the vehicle and the winch cable, he stops and waits for them to pass (for example, see Figure 2).
End of first shift	Marco's first shift is completed, and he returns to a small hut on the slope where he meets with some of his colleagues for dinner.

Figure 1: Screenshot: Snow groomer moving up the slope, winch is visible in top left corner.

Figure 2: Screenshot: Skier can be seen going down the slope, despite it being closed.

2.3 Use case 2: Logistics

For UC2, we created a problem scenario around fictional reach stacker operator Matias on a typical work day. This problem scenario is based on our observations of two experienced reach stacker test drivers in a KALMAR test area in Ljungby, Sweden, and an additional online discussion with an experienced reach stacker operator and a terminal manager working at the Port of Hanko, Finland.

Table 4: UC2 problem scenario

Event	Story
Preparations	<p>Winter has arrived in Finland and snow has fallen overnight. Reach stacker operator Matias checks the weather forecast and consults with his colleagues and superiors whether it's safe to work in the port area today. They agree it's safe and work can start as planned. The group quickly discusses who will take which vehicle on which shift and whether there are any closed areas of the port. Then, Matias puts on his protective clothing and enters the port area. He gets into a car with a colleague to get to the parking lot of the reach stacker he has been assigned to today.</p>
Start of operation	<p>Matias conducts a first inspection of the reach stacker today, checking the vehicle for tire damage, ice on the roof, oil leaks and sufficient oil levels. He then climbs up the vehicle, sits down in the driver's seat and adjusts it. He checks some of the vehicle's parameters on a small screen, such as fuel, oil temperature and the gearbox. The vehicle's heaters slowly warm up both the cabin and engine oil and everything seems to be in order. He first steers the reach stacker out of the parking area and checks the monitor for his assigned jobs. He selects a job and determines the area where he needs to pick up a container. For his first job, it's in a far corner of the port that is usually handled by one of his colleagues, who is on sick leave today.</p> <p>Before he sets off, Matias ensures that the spreader is in a good position to drive safely. He uses the joystick to move the spreader to the driving position. Since the night has been very cold, Matias does a few laps with the reach stacker to warm up all the components, then sets off to the first container. He relies largely on the mental map in his head and only has the support of a static map of the port area, which he can call up using the monitor. But since he rarely goes to this end of the port, it takes him a while to find the right spot where the container is located.</p>
Pick up container	<p>During the journey to the job site, Matias often checks the cabin windows and the mirrors to make sure that there are no people, cars, trucks, containers or other reach stacker drivers in his path. Finally, he arrives at his destination and checks the label on the container to see if it matches the one in the order. He approaches the container and moves the spreader into a suitable working position. He then aligns the spreader so that the twist locks are above the recesses in the containers. He is already quite proficient at this, but envies some of his more experienced colleagues, who can do it much faster.</p> <p>As soon as the positioning looks right, Matias lowers the spreader towards the container and activates the AutoLock function. He can tell the status of the locking mechanism from the green, yellow or red lights on the spreader. As soon as Matias places the spreader on the container, the lights switch from red to yellow to green.</p>

	<p>This signals that the locking mechanism is active and the container is now safely attached to the spreader.</p> <p>Matias now lifts the spreader, reverses and checks the side mirrors and rear windows and cameras several times to make sure his route is clear. At the same time, he uses the joystick to bring the spreader and boom into a suitable driving position.</p>
<p>Placement on truck trailer</p>	<p>Matias now heads towards the location where he is supposed to transfer the container on a truck trailer. His view is not always ideal, as there are many tall container stacks in his area and there is only a narrow aisle in between.</p> <p>Matias identifies the truck driver using the license plate number that was transmitted to him via the order. He approaches the truck from the side. He uses the horn and a hand gesture to signal the truck driver to align himself so that Matias can place the trailer. Instead of reversing, the truck driver drives one more lap around the reach stacker and then approaches again from the right side to reach a suitable position.</p> <p>Matias again uses the horn to signal when the truck driver is in the perfect position and can stop the truck. The truck driver leaves the cabin now. Matias then moves boom and spreader towards the truck trailer until he sees that the container is positioned correctly above the trailer. He lowers the container and makes fine adjustments. The truck driver manually checks the locks of the container in all four corners of the trailer. Then he signals that everything is OK. Now he releases the AutoLock function and the lights switch from green to yellow to red. Matias waits until the driver is back in his cab and only then moves away from the truck driver to his next job.</p>
<p>40ft container transfer</p>	<p>Again, Matias has to reverse and looks in the side mirrors and over his shoulder and cameras to make sure his route is clear. He moves spreader and boom back into driving position. On his way to the next job, he encounters several of his colleagues in other reach stackers and some truck drivers who sometimes appear unexpectedly behind a stack of containers. Matias is driving carefully, looking out for other vehicles.</p> <p>Finally, he arrives at his destination. This time he has to place a 40ft container on an existing stack (see Figure 1). He adjusts the spreader to its maximum width by pressing a button while approaching the container head-on. He moves his driver's cabin backwards to get a better view of the twist locks in the corners of the container. Matias again places the spreader and lowers it, but this time finds it more difficult to align the spreader with the container, since the twist locks are further away to the sides for picking up the wide container. After a few more attempts, he completes the AutoLock and lifts the container as soon as the green light on the upper beam of the cabin is visible (see Figure 2).</p> <p>He moves the spreader and boom back into transport position, reverses and heads towards the new destination. On the way, he has to drive very carefully in order not to collide with any other container stacks or tip over, since the 40ft container is extremely heavy. While turning around a sharp corner a little too quickly, Matias feels that the machine shortly becomes a little unstable. Once arrived, he places the 40ft container on the designated stack.</p>
<p>End of first shift</p>	<p>After transferring and stacking innumerable containers, Matias returns the reach stacker to a parking space near the main terminal building for lunch break. There</p>

he meets with some of his colleagues who worked on the port and they exchange their experiences of the day so far.

Figure 3: Reach stacker moving a 40ft container

Figure 4: Cabin view, lifting a 20ft container

2.4 Use case 3: Construction

For UC3, we created a problem scenario around fictional excavator operator Jonas on a typical workday. This problem scenario is based on our observations of two experienced excavator operators, three research associates with intermediate operating experience and one layman with very little operating experience.

Table 5: UC3 problem scenario

Scenario chapter	Story
Start of the day	Jonas arrives at the construction site, where he is instructed by his supervisor to dig a small rectangular hole where water pipes in the ground need to be maintained. The location is already marked.
Preparations	Jonas starts the engine and checks if all the systems are working. He moves the excavator to the indicated area and lowers the front blade for added stability. Before starting, Jonas defines the height, the shape, and the workspace of the excavation pit in the onboard software system.
Pit excavation	Jonas selects two from different views of the 3D model in the onboard software system which he finds suitable for the job and his personal preference when placed next to each other: Top and side view. He decides to start with the top right edge and start with the first dig there. Jonas moves the bucket filled with earth outside the excavation pit and empties the bucket there. As Jonas moves the excavator and work equipment back to the right, he is aware of people or obstacles around him since there is barely any visibility to the right. To ensure everything is fine on the backside, he is checking the cameras. While excavating, his focus is alternating between the excavation pit, the bucket, and the onboard software system to ensure that he is digging the right shape and with the correct depth (for example, see Figure 5).
Correction of settings	Jonas notices that he has made a small mistake: He has measured one measuring point (bottom right) of the excavation pit too close, because he is standing in the area of the embankment. After noticing this, he redoes the measuring of the two marking points at the bottom edge of the workspace respectively the excavation pit. To ensure, that everything went fine with the new measurements, he does an accuracy check. Jonas continues with digging out the predefined pit.
Trench excavation	Jonas moves the excavator to another excavation pit. There he does the same procedure for preparations and pre-settings as before and restarts his work in that area. Here, he needs to dig a trench for a pipeline. He starts by aligning the excavator centred and parallel to the direction of the planned trench. He digs up the soil in several layers, slowly approximating the desired depth, and unloads the bucket around 1 metre to the right of the trench to leave enough room for moving the vehicle to that position again, if needed (for example, see Figure 6). When the trench has reached the desired depth in his comfortable working distance, he swivels the swing around by 180 degrees to the left and reverses the vehicle by a few metres, then swivels around to the left again to continue digging.
End of first shift	Jonas places the bucket on the ground, moving boom, arm, and bucket away so that the hydraulic cylinders are as little extended as possible to protect them from bad weather. He releases the control lever to lock all moving parts, lowers the gas, powers down the engine, and exits the cabin. Before

he can power down the machine, he now needs to wait for another minute until the AdBlue has been pumped out of the engine and the machine gives a high-pitched signal.

Figure 5: Screenshot: The red dot indicates the operator focusing their gaze on the bucket.

Figure 6: Screenshot: Operator is digging a trench and unloading the soil to the right.

3 Work environment threats analysis

In addition to the context of use analyses, we gathered information on threats to equipment, cargo or human life at the controls or in the work environment of the respective off-highway vehicles. These studies were coupled with the context of use analysis. In the following, we will describe the method used and the results for the analyses in all use cases.

3.1 Method

We used a variation of the Critical Incident Technique (CIT)[4] to learn which types of threats can currently arise in the work environment of the respective use cases, how these dangerous situations occur and how to handle them (see table 4). Our variation of the method focused not on evaluating the performance of the operators but on understanding the details and correct management of these situations to be able to mitigate some of these threats with technology. The CIT was conducted in terms of structured interviews before or after the contextual inquiries. Only experienced operators were chosen for this study due to their profound and experiential knowledge on how to avoid dangers and how to react correctly in the occurrence of dangerous situations.

In the CIT interviews, we asked the operators to name up to three safety threats or potentially dangerous situations that can occur at the controls of the respective machines. Each of the threats and situations named was analysed using the guidelines laid out in Table 6

Table 6: Structure of questions in the CIT interviews

Question asked	Purpose
Please tell a story of what happened.	Encourages the operators to tell a story from their memory about a (potentially) dangerous situation that they experienced themselves or heard about from colleagues. Serves to give the operators a moment to recall the situation in detail, talk freely about the situation and possibly pre-empt some of the following questions.
How does this situation occur?	Clarifies the conditions for this kind of situation to occur.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Clarifies the severity of the threat posed by this situation: Threat to equipment, cargo, or human life.
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Helps clarify if certain procedures or technological solutions may mitigate the risk, and by extension, whether the mitigation of this type of threat may be targeted by developments in THEIA ^{XR} .
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Clarifies the ideal behaviour of operators, which may in future be assisted by technologies to be developed in THEIA ^{XR} .
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	Clarifies which possible errors must be prevented to make the damage avoidance procedure safe and successful. Relevant for the design of potential assisting technologies.

3.2 Use case 1: Snow grooming

For UC1, a total of five threats were discussed and analysed in depth. In the following tables, we describe these threats according to the structure outlined in table 4.

Table 7: UC1 – Loss of vision

Threat: Loss of vision due to fog or storm	
How does this situation occur?	Bad weather can occur anytime, fog is more likely when working on a glacier in summer.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to or even loss of vehicle if accidentally driving off the slope and over a creek or into a crevasse, possibly even threat to life if accidentally steering onto a frozen lake.
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Checking the weather forecast, however, weather can change quickly. Crevasses are difficult or even impossible to see in summer.
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Use the snow measurement system (roughly showing the position of the vehicle on the slope) to navigate. Use landmarks such as trees for orientation, if possible. If vehicle ends up on a frozen lake: Leave vehicle immediately when you hear ice cracking. If the vehicle is breaking in: Open the window to let the water in, then open door to escape.
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	N/A

Table 8: UC1 – Loss of traction

Threat: Loss of traction (vehicle starts sliding)	
How does this situation occur?	Winch rope may snap during operation on a steep slope; or the operator may accidentally approach the transition zone of a slope too fast or go too far over the edge.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Machine may flip and get damaged if sliding off a wall, resulting in minor injuries to the operator; people working on the slope (on foot) can be at risk if the machine slides towards them.
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Approaching the transition at the right speed and keeping distance from the edges of a slope; using the right machine for the job (steep slope requires vehicle with winch)
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Try to turn the vehicle around (facing forward) while sliding, put the blade down to increase traction.
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	Letting the tracks come to a stop or using the hand brake (further reducing traction), releasing the hands from the controls.

Table 9: UC1 – Avalanche

Threat: Descent of an avalanche	
How does this situation occur?	E.g., when working on a glacier with heavy snowfall and wind, vibration of the machine or movement of the winch rope under the snow may trigger an avalanche.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	When inside the vehicle, minor risk to the operator. When outside of the vehicle, major risk.
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	As snow groomer operator, there is little one can do. Slopes with avalanche risk are usually closed. Avalanche risk of a slope is difficult to assess with the bare eyes. A lot of fresh snow, wind, or wet snow (due to higher temperatures in spring) may be indicators.
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	If outside of the vehicle, immediately head inside.
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	N/A

Table 10: Skier accidents

Threat: Accidents involving skiers on the slope	
How does this situation occur?	Skiers are regularly still going down slopes even after closing hours. Snow groomer operator may be focused on the slope in front of him and pay less attention to the mirrors. Skiers may crash behind the vehicle due to torn open snow surface, in that case they have near zero chances to be noticed by the operator.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Major injuries to the skiers, or even threat to life, especially when crashing behind the vehicle.
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	In some cases, known areas (e.g., ski huts) with increased activity can be groomed later. Operators must always pay attention to mirrors and cameras.
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	When skiers are spotted nearby: Stop the vehicle and call attention to it, wait until the skiers have passed.
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	N/A

Table 11: UC1 – Obstacle accidents

Threat: Accidents involving obstacles on the slope	
How does this situation occur?	During moments of heedlessness, fatigue, or distraction, especially when working with bad vision. In fog, contours of objects on the slope can be difficult to distinguish. When looking down to the screen or to the back of the vehicle.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to property
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Onboard GPS device allows operators to see their own position on the slope and its edges, and may even include stationary objects (e.g., stationary snow cannons)
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Stop the vehicle
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	N/A

3.3 Use case 2: Logistics

For UC2, a total of three threats was discussed and analysed in depth. In the following tables, we describe these threats according to the structure outlined in Table 6.

Table 12: UC2 – Tipping over

Threat: Vehicle tipping over	
How does this situation occur?	While transporting a heavy container and braking too hard or while driving on inclines (rare)
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to machine and cargo, threat to life for people near the machine
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	When lifting heavy weights, keeping vehicle speed at minimum; paying attention to warning system that indicates when cargo is too heavy
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	N/A
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	N/A

Table 13: UC2 – Loss of traction

Threat: Loss of traction (vehicle starts slipping)	
How does this situation occur?	When temperatures are frequently changing, causing wet or frozen surfaces; on sandy surfaces
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to machine and cargo when sliding into other vehicles or containers, otherwise mainly threat to life for people near the machine
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Can be foreseen and reacted to based on weather forecasts; use of spiked tires or salt on frozen surfaces
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Soft braking instead of hard braking
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	N/A

Table 14: UC2 – Person accidents

Threat: Accidents involving people near the vehicle (especially truck drivers)	
How does this situation occur?	Mainly caused by persons being overlooked because of blind spots behind each tire or behind the hydraulic cylinders; possibly also a false sense of security from the assumption that reach stacker operator will see everything near the vehicle on a camera screen
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Threat to life for people near the machine
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Checking the back of the vehicle and cameras before reversing
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	If people near the vehicle are seen, immediately stop and inform them to stand back in a safe area
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	Nervous or angry behaviour, e. g., using the horn, may lead to persons near the vehicle being shocked and/or acting unpredictably, possibly putting themselves in greater danger

3.4 Use case 3: Construction

For UC3, a total of five threats were discussed and analysed in depth. In the following tables, we describe these threats according to the structure outlined in table 4.

Table 15: UC3 – Vehicle collisions

Threat: Collisions with other vehicles	
How does this situation occur?	When reversing without looking or paying attention to the cameras, happens more easily under stress or time pressure
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to property, in rare cases total loss of the vehicle or injuries to the operators
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Deployment of a banksman, using light signals (to raise attention) or radio communication, paying attention to reversing aid (if available). Swivel around the swing of the excavator to the left until the vehicle faces backwards (to drive “forward” in backwards rotation)
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Stop the vehicle, get out and talk with the operator of the other vehicle to discuss how to move the vehicles apart safely
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	Incorrect operation of the controls in rush, accidentally running the vehicle further into the other (due to possibly reversed orientation of the vehicle)

Table 16: UC3 – Tilting

Threat: Vehicle tilting	
How does this situation occur?	When working on a slope, soft ground may crumble, causing the vehicle to tip. Operator may also be misjudging the physical limits of the vehicle (e.g., too heavy load in bucket)
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Vehicle may flip, resulting in material damage and, if the operator is not using the seat belts, threat to life
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Keeping a safety distance from edges of slopes; internalisation of operating manual and careful approximation of physical limits of the vehicle. Only working on possibly dangerous slopes if the weather allows it – soft or wet ground is risky. In dry conditions, risk is minimal. Choosing the right vehicle for the job – not too large, not too heavy.
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	If ground crumbles, try to move away from the area. If vehicle tilts, use the arm and bucket of the excavator to support the vehicle. Reduce the angle of boom and arm to stabilize the vehicle (moving the centre of weight closer to the vehicle)
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	Incorrect operation of the controls in rush, swivelling the swing to the wrong side, reducing stability of the vehicle even further

Table 17: UC3 – Contact with overhead electrical lines

Threat: Contact with overhead electrical lines	
How does this situation occur?	Not paying attention when swivelling while working below an overhead electrical line.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to property, threat to life, especially if the electrical line rips and falls into the cabin or on a nearby person
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Overhead lines are clearly visible. They can be isolated by the provider company in advance of construction, however, that may take several weeks due to bureaucracy. Specialized excavators have a hoist limiting system which eliminates the risk of hitting overhead electrical lines, but these are not always provided by the construction company.
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Lower the boom and have the bucket touch the ground (to earth the vehicle)
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	Swivelling further or raising the boom even further

Table 18: UC3 – Contact with cables and lines in the ground

Threat: Contact with electrical lines, gas lines or water lines in the ground	
How does this situation occur?	When doing construction work in residential areas. Usually there are indicators for cables and lines in the ground (streamers and sand layers in the ground), but these are often inaccurate. Especially older cables and lines are rarely marked. Communal plans of the position of cables and lines in the ground are also often inaccurate.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to property and threat to life: Hitting electrical lines could result in an arc flash or jet of flame and turn the vehicle into a Faraday cage (wheeled excavator only). Hitting gas lines may cause the vehicle to catch fire. Hitting water lines poses a lower risk, but the escaping water could wash away the ground and cause it to crumble, resulting in a risk of tilting the vehicle.
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Difficult to foresee and prevent due to inaccuracies of plans and markings. Excavating slowly and paying attention to changing soil types may help to recognize the protective gravel or sand around cables and lines.
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	The respective provider companies must be contacted, electrical power must be turned off before it is safe to exit the vehicle (in case of Faraday cage). In case of fire, the vehicle must be exited quickly. In case of escaping water, the vehicle should be moved away before the ground is washed away.
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	If an electrical line has been hit: Exiting the vehicle in a rush while it is still live poses a threat to life.

Table 19: UC3 – Collisions in the swivelling range

Threat: Collisions with objects or persons in the swivelling range	
How does this situation occur?	When swivelling to the right (where vision is severely limited) due to limited space to the left or bad vehicle positioning. In some cases, pedestrians may move barriers and enter the construction area.
What kind of danger can arise from this situation?	Damage to property, injuries, and threat to life for people in the swivelling range.
Can this situation be foreseen or prevented? If so, how?	Correct positioning (to be able to swivel to the left), choosing the right vehicle for the job. Sensitisation of the construction site personnel to stay clear of the swivelling area and deployment of a banksman (responsibility of the construction company). Fencing off the danger zone. Paying attention to the surroundings of the vehicle.
If that situation occurs, which steps must be taken in order to avoid damage?	Place down the bucket on the ground, releasing the control lever (safety feature to lock all functions of the vehicle), turn down the engine power, get out of the vehicle. Expel pedestrians from the construction site.
Are there any errors that could happen while taking these steps that would make it more difficult to avoid damage or present a new dangerous situation itself?	Without releasing the control lever, an operator trying to lean out of the cabin and signal persons to pass nearby or in front of the vehicle may accidentally hit one of the levers for operating the tracks or swing, moving of swivelling the vehicle.

4 Conclusions

The context of use analysis has provided the researchers with invaluable insights into typical working situations, behaviours, decisions, and habits at the controls of the respective vehicles. Many, but not all of these insights could be integrated into the problem scenarios so far due to the complexity of these workplaces and the richness of details that can or must be paid attention to.

There are also similarities between the use cases. For example, we have observed that staying focused on the terrain in front of the vehicle and the vehicle's interaction with that terrain (e.g., the snow groomer blade in the snow or the excavator bucket in the soil) is essential for good work results. However, to avoid accidents with other vehicles, obstacles or even humans, paying attention to the vehicle mirrors and camera screens (to watch the rear and sides of the vehicle) is necessary as well. On top of that, precise operation often also requires checking on certain information screens (e.g., showing current snow depth or desired pit depth). This means there are three competing and essential sources of information for the human operators, who – at the same time as trying to pay attention to all of these – need a lot of skill to correctly operate the controls of their respective machines, which usually involve two or more joysticks and pedals. With this in view, it becomes clear that simply adding more screens or displaying more information on the existing would not be a viable solution. This is where appropriately selected and designed XR technologies could bring serious improvements, reducing the cognitive load on human operators and providing them with the information they need in readily understandable means – which might not only be visual in nature.

The problem scenarios should be understood as living documents and subject to change over the course of the next months. However, in the current state, they already provide a realistic visualization of typical working tasks, procedures, and events at the controls of the respective off-highway vehicles. They will make it easier for consortium partners and stakeholders to ideate new technologies and interaction concepts that solve specific problems while keeping in mind the working context that these technologies and concepts must fit in seamlessly with. The collected information will also be used for updating and fine tuning the use case specifications. This will form the basis for deciding which technologies will be developed to target the identified challenges/dangers presented to the human operators in the different use cases. Specifically, we expect initial ideation sessions involving the use-case leads and technology providers to result in some first rough concepts (activity scenarios) of what would be technically feasible. These concepts will then serve as inspiration for use-case-specific co-design sessions involving real human operators, who can expand upon these concepts or explore entirely new ideas, which will then again need to be assessed for their feasibility by technical partners. In this manner, there will be several iterations of XR technology ideation and discussion between project consortium and human operators until we have validated concepts ready for further development, i.e., information- and interaction scenario development and early prototyping.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

CIT	Critical Incident Technique
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
M	Month
UC	Use Case
XR	Extended Reality